

CLIMATE - RAPID EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

UNCERTAINTY CHECKLIST

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Bibliographic Information

This report should be cited as: Hegedűs, D., Swaminathan, R. and Woolliams, E. (2025). Climate–Rapid Evaluation Framework Uncertainty Checklist version 1.0. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17312883>

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Acknowledgements

The contents of this checklist were reviewed by a group of experts led by the UK's National Metrology Institute, the National Physical Laboratory (NPL), at a dedicated workshop on uncertainty metadata held at the University of Reading on the 19 August 2025. A number of changes were made as a result. The final draft of this checklist was reviewed by Emma Woolliams (NPL, ESMO/WGORG).

The workshop participants were:

Alison Pamment (CEDA STFC / NCAS), Briony Turner (CMIP International Project Office), Chris Merchant (University of Reading), Claire Bulgin (University of Reading), Colin Morice (Met Office) David Hassell (NCAS / University of Reading), Dóra Hegedűs (STFC / CMIP IPO – Climate-REF, WGORG), Emma Woolliams (NPL, WGORG), Forrest Hoffman (ORNL & CMIP Model Benchmarking TT co-lead), Jonathan Mittaz (University of Reading & NPL), Kate Willett (Met Office), Luke Abraham (NCAS / University of Cambridge), Maria Caffrey (NPL), Michael Chrubasik (NPL), Olivier Burggraaff (NPL), Owen Embury (University of Reading), Pieter De Vis (NPL), Ranjini Swaminathan (University of Reading, NCEO & CMIP Model Benchmarking Task Team co-lead), Sam Hunt (NPL, CEOS) and Swen Brands (CSIC-UC, CMIP Model Benchmarking Task Team, CORDEX).

This has also been reviewed for alignment with [obs4MIPs data specifications](#) (ODS) by Paul Smith, CMIP IPO.

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Checklist of uncertainty information for observational data sets on ESGF being used by the Rapid Evaluation Framework (REF)

Document Purpose:

This document describes the treatment of uncertainties within observational datasets with the intention of using this information within the REF, as agreed upon by the obs4MIPs Steering Panel and the CMIP REF Delivery Team.

This approach enables the REF to demonstrate, with concrete examples, how a wider range of observational uncertainty can be incorporated for climate model evaluation.

Checklist:

- ✓ Each additional uncertainty information is provided in a separate file if prepared by CMOR. We expect there to be between 1–3 additional files depending on the extent of uncertainty information given. If not prepared by CMOR, the uncertainty information can be given in the same file as the main geophysical variable following the [CF conventions for including ancillary variables](#).
- ✓ NetCDF file containing the main geophysical variable has global attribute “has_aux_unc”, and is set to TRUE when additional files containing uncertainty information are provided or when uncertainty information is provided as ancillary variables in the same file as the main geophysical variable. It should be set to FALSE when no uncertainty information is provided. If this attribute does not exist, the REF will assume there is no uncertainty information provided.
- ✓ If has_aux_unc is set to TRUE, NetCDF file containing the main geophysical variable has global attribute “aux_uncertainty_id”. This contains all additional variable_id+uncertainty suffixes for the uncertainty information provided, in the form of a string with spaces as delimiters.
- ✓ Global attribute “variable_id” of file containing the uncertainty information corresponds to variable name+accepted suffix if uncertainty information is provided in separate files. For accepted suffixes, see Table 1.
- ✓ Variable name within the NetCDF file corresponds to variable_id.
- ✓ Technical note provides detailed explanation of each additional uncertainty information provided, including type of uncertainty. The note should discuss what is included in the total uncertainty, by providing a breakdown of its components; such as sources of independent, structured/correlated and common uncertainty.

Preparing your dataset:

Obs4MIPs requests datasets to be prepared with CMOR (Climate Model Output Rewriter), which currently does not allow more than one variable per file. This means that any uncertainty fields associated with the observational dataset have to be provided as a separate file. As described in the obs4MIPs Data Specification document, version 2.6: <https://zenodo.org/records/17235676>, the REF requires some additional global attributes so that it can ingest the uncertainty information. The following global attributes are required within the file containing the main geophysical variable e.g. "pr":

- "has_aux_unc" – boolean type, TRUE means uncertainty information is provided, FALSE means no uncertainty information is provided, always required
- "aux_uncertainty_id" – string type, space as delimiters, e.g. "prstd prnobs" or "prlwnd prubnd prnobs", only required if "has_aux_unc = TRUE"

For any additional files containing uncertainty information, the REF has the following requirements:

- Global attribute "variable_id" of file containing the uncertainty information corresponds to variable name + accepted suffix, e.g. for the standard uncertainty of precipitation use "prstd". For accepted suffixes, see Table 1. We understand this list is restrictive in its current version, and we hope to expand it in the future (e.g. Table 2). However, this was outside the scope of the REF AFT due to its time constraint.
- Variable name within the NetCDF file, as well as the data reference syntax, should correspond to the variable_id+suffix.

Preliminary examples of uncertainty information included within the same file:

1. When the uncertainty components are provided.

Note: these examples may change (no standards set, but recommended metadata to include):

variables:

// Data variable

```
float pr(lat, lon, time) ;  
pr:standard_name = "precipitation_flux" ;  
pr:units = "kg m-2 s-1" ;  
pr:ancillary_variables = "prustd pruind prustr prucum" ;
```

// Uncertainty ancillary variables

```
float prustd(lat, lon, time) ;  
ustd:standard_name = "precipitation_flux" ;  
ustd:long_name = "Standard uncertainty" ;  
ustd:units = "kg m-2 s-1" ;  
ustd:uncertainty_interval = "standard_deviation" ;  
  
float pruind(lat, lon, time) ;  
uind:standard_name = "precipitation_flux" ;  
uind:long_name = "Uncertainty due to independent effects" ;  
uind:units = "kg m-2 s-1" ;  
uind:uncertainty_interval = "standard_deviation" ;
```

```
float prustr(lat, lon, time) ;  
ustr:standard_name = "precipitation_flux" ;  
ustr:long_name = "Uncertainty due to structured effects" ;  
ustr:units = "kg m-2 s-1" ;  
ustr:uncertainty_interval = "standard_deviation" ;  
ustr:correlation_length_scale = "..."
```

```
float prucum(lat, lon, time) ;  
ucum:standard_name = "precipitation_flux" ;  
ucum:long_name = "Uncertainty due to common effects" ;  
ucum:units = "kg m-2 s-1" ;  
ucum:uncertainty_interval = "standard_deviation" ;
```

2. When the uncertainty has an asymmetric distribution.

Note: these examples may change (no standards set, but recommended metadata to include):

variables:

// Data variable

```
float pr(lat, lon, time);  
pr:standard_name = "precipitation_flux";  
pr:units = "kg m-2 s-1";  
pr:ancillary_variables = "prubnd prlbdn";
```

// Uncertainty ancillary variables

```
float prubnd(lat, lon, time);  
ubnd:standard_name = "precipitation_flux";  
ubnd:units = "kg m-2 s-1";  
ubnd:uncertainty_interval = "upper_bound";  
ubnd:uncertainty_level_of_confidence = 0.9;
```

```
float prlbdn(lat, lon, time);  
lbnd:standard_name = "precipitation_flux";  
lbnd:units = "kg m-2 s-1";  
lbnd:uncertainty_interval = "lower_bound";  
lbnd:uncertainty_level_of_confidence = 0.9;
```

Writing the Technical Note:

The obs4MIPs Steering Panel have a guidance document for writing the technical note here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14276262>. In the section describing the uncertainties, please provide a description of all uncertainty information provided with your dataset, and if applicable, the breakdown of uncertainty components and the propagation of the uncertainty when re-gridding or aggregating the dataset during model evaluation. Please also discuss any sampling biases that might need to be considered for model evaluation, such as diurnal cycle or cloud cover.

Table 1: List of suffixes for including additional uncertainty information in obs4MIPs (most current version of table).

Suffix	Long name	Description
nobs	Number of observations	The number of discrete observations or measurements from which a data value has been derived.
ustd	Standard uncertainty	The per-datum standard uncertainty is a combination of independent, structured and common effects and is equal to the positive square root of the sum of the components. The standard uncertainty is provided at one standard deviation. Replacement for “standard error” due to updated terminology.
stderr	Standard error	Legacy term used for backward compatibility. Definition is identical to that of the standard uncertainty.
uind	Uncertainty due to independent effects	The per-datum component of uncertainty that is associated with uncorrelated effects, provided at one standard deviation.
ustr	Uncertainty due to structured effects	The per-datum component of uncertainty that is structured and correlated over a defined space/time scale, provided at one standard deviation. This correlation length scale in space and time must be provided in the variable metadata.
ucom	Uncertainty due to common effects	The per-datum component of uncertainty that is common to all observations of a given type (specific instrument, resolution, variable type) at one standard deviation.
lbnd	Lower bound of asymmetrical uncertainty information	Alternative to stderr or ustd for observations with asymmetrical uncertainty distribution, lower bound of the uncertainty interval.
ubnd	Upper bound of asymmetrical uncertainty information	Alternative to stderr or ustd for observations with asymmetrical uncertainty distribution, upper bound of the uncertainty interval.

Checklist preparation

Expert review

The contents of the version 1.0 checklist were reviewed by a group of experts led by NPL at a dedicated [workshop on uncertainty metadata](#) held at the University of Reading on the 19 August 2025. A number of changes to Table 1 were made as a result. The final draft of this checklist was reviewed by Emma Woolliams (NPL, ESMO/WGORC).

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V1.0 document preparation

- Requirement for checklist established during REF Hackathon 10–13 March 2025
- Initial draft by Dora Hegedus on 20th March 2025
- Edits by Ranjini Swaminathan on 21st March and by Dora Hegedus on 24th March 2025
- Table 1 shared with community in [Github #188](#) 24 March 2025
- Discussed and issued for review at obs4MIPs Steering Panel meeting 26 March 2025
- Updated by Dora Hegedus on 21st July, 20th August and by Ranjini Swaminathan on 25th September
- Reviewed by CMIP Panel 02 October 2025
- Finalised for publication by Ranjini Swaminathan 13 and 17 November 2025
- V1.0 published 21 November 2025

Version Record

Version number	Change description from previous version	Rationale/Justification	Authorising body
1.0	NA, first version		CMIP Panel